

Field Course in High-Resolution Sequence Stratigraphy (Lusitanian Basin, Portugal)

cyclicality and reservoir zonation in
shallow-marine setting

Field Course in Sequence Stratigraphy (Lusitanian Basin, Portugal): cyclicality and reservoir zonation in shallow-marine setting

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1. Introduction and Objectives

A field course guide in sequence stratigraphy in the Lusitanian Basin has hitherto never been published, despite the world-class outcrops and several studies encompassing several aspects of the Lusitanian Basin geology. This field guide includes texts and figures from the recently published paper by Magalhães et al., (2023). Therefore, this guide focuses on the Middle Jurassic succession that crops out between the villages of Consolação and São Bernardino along the Atlantic coast. This 170 m thick mostly shallow-marine succession exhibits remarkable cyclicality that enables applying high-resolution sequence stratigraphy to reservoir zonation and characterization.

Sequence stratigraphy is a method based on the identification and correlation of stratal stacking patterns in the sedimentary record (Catuneanu, 2022). Such an approach helps understand sedimentation evolution through time and space in sedimentary basins. Currently, the stratigraphic analysis that supports the exploration and production of natural resources are founded on comprehending the sedimentary processes that generated the deposits and their bounding surfaces (Magalhães et al., 2021). The exploration and production of natural resources generated by or related to sedimentary processes depend upon building chronostratigraphic frameworks that allow palaeogeographic reconstructions, which in turn improve our knowledge about the temporal and spatial distribution of source rocks, seals and petroleum reservoirs, and other natural resources deposits.

Based on observations on outcrops, the field course has a methodological and practical objective aimed at recognising stacking patterns and identifying sequence stratigraphic surfaces and sequences of variable hierarchies. Participants use Virtual Outcrop Models (VOMs) to integrate all data they gather through facies analysis and Gamma Ray logs from outcrops. As a result, participants build a chronostratigraphic framework at low-, middle-, and high-frequency to focus on the reservoir scale. In vogue in the petroleum industry, this approach is also applied to other natural resources production optimisation, C and H storage and pollutants injection. The expected gain in stratigraphic analysis skills will help participants deal with other outcrops, well logs, cores, and seismic data of sedimentary successions preserved worldwide.

At the end of the course, participants are expected to:

- Grasp the sequence stratigraphy principles and methodology;
- Build chronostratigraphic frameworks suitable to the exploration and production of petroleum and other natural resources, storage of C and H, and pollutants injection;

- Apply high-resolution sequence stratigraphy to reservoir zonation and characterisation or other natural resource. Comprehend the impact sequence stratigraphy has on fluid injection and production performance of hydrocarbons and other natural resources;
- deposits.

1.1. Study area

The Lusitanian Basin is located on both the mainland and continental shelf off the west-central coast of Portugal. The study interval comprises the outcropping succession of the Candeeiros Formation between the villages of Consolação and São Bernardino, in the southern flank of the Consolação anticline (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. (A,B) Location of the course area, at the Western Lusitanian Basin, Portugal. (C) Field activities are concentrated along a continuously exposed 1.8 km long and 180 m thick succession at the littoral (red line). (D) Overall current tectonic configuration of the Lusitanian Basin (modified from Taylor et al., 2014 and Pimentel and Pena dos Reis, 2016).

Strata consist of shallow-marine grey to greenish siltstone, light cream sandstone, and cream carbonate rocks dipping 8° S. This colour pattern contrasts with the light-grey sandstone and red to brown siltstone from the Upper Jurassic continental Lourinhã Formation seen further south. The contact between these units is well exposed at São Bernardino beach (Taylor et al., 2014) and corresponds to the Middle-Upper Jurassic disconformity. Hence, it marks the top of the studied succession. The course area is located on a faulted anticline in its northern portion, whose axis is situated in the village of Consolação (Fig. 1C). This normal

fault (i.e., Consolação Fault) marks the base of the studied succession, dips towards the north-east and strikes N43W, making part of a fault zone whose traces are observed on the beach ground and in the cliff (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Consolação Fault 3D model (see location on Fig. 1C). (A) VOM map view shows the fault zone (north-western oriented traces on the ground). (B) Fault plane and damage zone crop out in the cliff at the south end of Consolação village. (C) Consolação Fault 3D geometrical model showing the apparent fault throw. The Consolação Fort is located on the footwall whereas the Consolação village rests on the hanging-wall block. (D) Structural cross-section highlights the correlative conformities (CC, coloured lines). The correlation of CC5 between the foot- and hanging-wall blocks indicates a fault throw of 50 m.

2. Agenda

Day 1: Morning, 10 am - Meeting participants at Lisbon airport and drive to Consolação. Afternoon activities (Hotel): course schedule and classes on the Lusitanian Basin and review of sequence stratigraphy. Exercise: interpretation of outcrop orthophotos.

Day 2: Morning – Field activity: description of clastic marine and carbonate successions, interpretation of stacking patterns and stratigraphic surfaces. Afternoon: Visiting the GSSP base of Toarcian stage, Peniche. Hotel: data integration.

Day 3: Morning – Field activity: description of clastic marine and carbonate successions, interpretation of stacking patterns and stratigraphic surfaces. Hotel: data integration.

Day 4: Morning – Field activity: description of clastic marine and fluvial successions, interpretation of stacking patterns and stratigraphic surfaces. Hotel: data integration.

Day 5: Hotel. State of the art in the stratigraphic analysis of outcrops using virtual 3D models, gamma-ray logs and columnar sections. Exercises and closing. Drive to Lisbon airport at 4 pm.

3. Course methodology

This field course presents the up-to-date high-resolution sequence stratigraphy method. The method was consolidated by Petrobras High-Resolution Sequence Stratigraphy School (e.g., Fragozo et al., 2023, 2022, 2021; Magalhães et al., 2023, 2021, 2020; Melo et al., 2021, 2020). Besides, the course uses VOMs and GR logs to be integrated with data gathered by the participants (sedimentological, stratigraphic, and structural) to support their interpretations.

Before the fieldwork, participants use orthophotos and VOMs to interpret architectural elements and bounding surfaces, faults and fractures, and to indicate the location of sedimentological logs to be acquired on the outcrops. Once the sedimentological logs are ready, participants interpret the sequence stratigraphy surfaces and update their mapping on the orthophotos. Integrating all groups' sedimentological logs lead to a discussion regarding the surface's hierarchies and the individualisation of high-, medium- and low-frequency sequences.

The following methodological steps must be followed. Steps 1 to 3 and 8 are done at the Hotel. Steps 4 to 7 are done in the field:

Step 1: Delimiting architectural elements based on internal sedimentary structures and bounding surfaces on orthophotos and VOMs;

Step 2: Interpreting stratal stacking patterns and correlating high-resolution sequence stratigraphic surfaces;

Step 3: Defining the sedimentological logs' locations;

Step 4: Logging the outcrop. The sedimentological log must include depositional facies description and palaeocurrent directions;

Step 5: Characterisation of architectural elements. Depositional systems' interpretation;

Step 6: Interpreting stacking patterns based on the vertical recurrence of architectural elements;

Step 7: Identifying and correlating high-frequency sequence stratigraphic surfaces. Individualising high-frequency sequences on the sedimentological log, orthophoto and VOM. Comparing with the previous interpretation (Step 2);

Step 8: Integrating the sedimentological logs. Discussion about the candidate surfaces to be ranked at the immediately higher hierarchy and identification of their systems tracts.

4. Geodynamic evolution of the Lusitanian Basin

The Lusitanian Basin was formed during the breakup of Pangea and the subsequent opening of the North Atlantic (Wilson et al., 1989; Manspeizer, 2015). The dominant structural controls on its development follow the NNE and NW trends of the Caledonian-Variscan orogenic basement formed at the end of the Palaeozoic (Wilson et al., 1989; Pastor Galán et al., 2015). The Lusitanian Basin palaeogeographic position, close to the triple junction formed by the African, Iberian and North American plates (Fernandéz, 2019), conditioned its tectono-sedimentary evolution in two main rift phases between Newfoundland Grand Banks and the Iberia margin: the Late Triassic–Middle Jurassic rift 1 and Late Jurassic–Early Cretaceous rift 2 (Fig. 3; Tucholke et al., 2007). The influence of Tethys Ocean waters remained active during both rift phases. It controlled the distribution of organisms since there was no physical barrier preventing the free circulation of Tethys waters in the Lusitanian Basin even after the opening of the North Atlantic Ocean (Azêredo et al., 2002).

During the Late Triassic rift phase, continental red beds (Silves Formation) filled an extensive area of multiple half-graben basins (Pena dos Reis et al., 2017) that were eventually overlain by evaporites (Dagorda Formation) and a thick carbonate succession (Coimbra Formation, Brenha and Candeeiros groups; Wilson et al., 1989; Azerêdo, 1998; Tucholke et al., 2007; Leleu et al., 2016; Nirrengarten et al., 2017; Pena dos Reis et al., 2017). Most of the Early–Middle Jurassic was a time of relative tectonic quiescence characterising the post-rift stage with the development of a carbonate ramp depositional system (Azerêdo and Wright, 2004; Duarte et al., 2017).

The Middle–Upper Jurassic disconformity marks the end of the Late Triassic–Middle Jurassic rift phase. This event is related to a very prolonged extension episode that created a hyperextended rift and, probably, the oceanic crust between conjugated basin margins that evolved to continental breakup from the Barremian to the Aptian (Alves et al., 2002; Tucholke et al., 2007; Dinis et al., 2008; Manspeizer, 2015; Nirrengarten et al., 2017; Fernandéz, 2019; Causer et al., 2020). This extension created several sub-basins filled with carbonate platform deposits (Cabaços and Montejunto formations), mixed carbonate-clastic, basinal (Abadia Formation) and continental to shallow-marine (Alcobaça Formation) deposits, overlain by continental to coastal strata (Lourinhã and Farta Pão formations; Hill, 1988; Leinfelder and Wilson, 1998; Rasmussen et al., 1998; Alves et al., 2002; Dinis et al., 2008; Schneider and Fürsich, 2009; Mateus et al., 2013; Taylor et al., 2014). During the Late Cretaceous, the Iberian plate was subjected to compressional motion because of the convergence of Africa with Eurasia plates during the Alpine Orogeny. This event triggered the inversion of the Lusitanian Basin and, subsequently, the exposure of a significant part of its rift 1, post-rift, and rift 2 successions (Schettino and Turco, 2009; Terrinha et al., 2019).

Fig. 3. (A) Chronostratigraphic chart of the Upper Triassic–Jurassic interval from the Central Lusitanian Basin, tectonic events, and plate kinematics associated with North Atlantic–Central Atlantic–Tethys conjugated margin. The studied succession (highlighted in green) is part of the Candeeiros Formation, and the Middle–Upper Jurassic disconformity encompasses a middle Callovian–middle Oxfordian hiatus in this location. Salt diapir, in white, crosses all Jurassic units. Note the GSSP between at the base of Toarcian stage. (B) Schematic palaeogeographic reconstruction during early–Callovian. The positive topography created by salt domes delimited the occurrence of marine carbonates eastwards. The structural low between salt domes and the Berlingas horst trapped clastic sediments and delivered them southwards to the depocenter. Based on Alves et al. (2002), Tucholke et al. (2007), Azerêdo and Wright (2004), Schettino and Turco (2009), Mateus et al. (2013), Pena dos Reis and Pimentel (2014), and Taylor et al. (2014).

5. Facies associations of Consolação – São Bernardino succession

Following Magalhães et al., 2023, the Consolação – São Bernardino succession consists mainly of siltstone–sandstone alternations, less frequent carbonate, and rare mixed depositional facies (Tables 1 and 2). Siliciclastic facies associations (FA) occur throughout the succession. In contrast, carbonate FAs are limited to the lower part but with discrete occurrences (i.e., from 10 to 107 m). Facies associations consist of genetically related depositional facies that define a particular sedimentary environment. In the studied succession, facies associations represent sedimentation in a shallow-marine, offshore, and outer-shelf settings (Table 3).

Facies Code	Lithology and sedimentary structure	Description	Main process
Gm	Conglomerate massive	Dark grey, massive, disorganised, polymictic (quartz, feldspar, bivalve, siltstone clasts < 10cm, mud clasts < 1cm), macroforaminifera, matrix supported, fine-grained sandy matrix. Erosive basal contact.	Pseudoplastic debris flow (inertial bedload, turbulent flow) or deposition by high-density hyperconcentrated flow.
St	Sandstone trough cross-bedding	Cream to light grey, fine- to very fine-grained, trough to planar cross-bedding > 20cm thick. Coal fragments and bioclasts < 3cm. <i>Skolithos</i> ichnofacies, Bioturbation Index (BI) 2: <i>Skolithos</i> , <i>Psilonichnus</i> , <i>Arenicolites</i> , <i>Cylindrichnus</i> , <i>Diplocaterium</i> , <i>Ophiomorpha</i> . Abrupt top and basal contact.	Upper stage plane beds associated with migration of subaqueous 2D and 3D ripples under lower flow regime.
Sp	Sandstone planar cross-bedding	Light to dark grey, very coarse- to medium-grained, planar cross-bedding < 10cm thick. Also with granules, bivalve bioclasts, and mud clasts < 5cm. <i>Skolithos</i> ichnofacies, BI 3: <i>Skolithos</i> , <i>Arenicolites</i> , <i>Ophiomorpha</i> , <i>Cylindrichnus</i> . Erosive basal contact.	
Sh	Sandstone laminated	Cream to light grey, fine-grained, parallel lamination. Fining-up to very fine-grained and coal fragments (mm). Locally medium-grained to granular levels with bivalve bioclasts, macroforaminifera, and coal fragments < 2 up to > 15cm. <i>Girvanella</i> coating on bivalve. Locally bioturbated at the top, <i>Skolithos</i> ichnofacies, Bioturbation Index (BI) 2: <i>Skolithos</i> , <i>Psilonichnus</i> , <i>Arenicolites</i> , <i>Cylindrichnus</i> , <i>Diplocaterium</i> , <i>Ophiomorpha</i> . Abrupt basal contact.	
Shcs	Sandstone hummocky cross-stratification	Cream to light grey, fine-grained, hummocky cross-stratification. Elongated coal fragments < 15cm at the base and also < 2cm along the stratification sets. Erosive basal contact.	
Sc	Sandstone convoluted	Light grey, very coarse- grained to granular (quartz, feldspar, dark grains), convoluted, coal fragments < 1cm. Erosive basal contact.	Syn depositional deformation triggered by slump or seismic activity.
Sm	Sandstone massive	Light grey, fine- to very fine-grained, massive. Also with load structure. <i>Skolithos</i> ichnofacies, Bioturbation Index (BI) 2: <i>Skolithos</i> , <i>Psilonichnus</i> , <i>Arenicolites</i> , <i>Cylindrichnus</i> , <i>Diplocaterium</i> , <i>Ophiomorpha</i> . Abrupt basal contact.	Flows with high depositional rates suppressing grain traction.
Swr	Sandstone wave ripples	Cream to light grey, fine- to very fine-grained, with wave ripples at the top. Generally associated with fining-up trend. Gradational basal contact.	Interaction of oscillatory flows induced by surface waves close to the depositional surface.
Sr	Sandstone ripple cross-lamination	Cream to light grey, fine- to very fine-grained, with ripple cross-lamination at the top. Generally associated with Sh. Gradational basal contact.	Migration of subaqueous ripples under unidirectional flow, lower flow regime, above fair weather wave base level.
He	Heterolith	Light grey, composed of interbeds of very fine-grained sandstone and siltstone, top bioturbated BI 2, <i>Thalassinoides</i> . Gradational basal contact.	Alternation between deposition from traction and suspension followed by wave reworking.
Fl	Claystone to siltstone laminated	Grey to greenish, laminated, micaceous. Also bioturbated towards the top by <i>Thalassinoides isp</i> and <i>Thalassinoides saxonicus</i> , BI 2 to 5. Abrupt basal contact.	Deposition from suspension and ripples migration under unidirectional flow.
Fm	Claystone to siltstone massive	Grey to light brown, massive, micaceous, coal fragments (mm). Abrupt basal contact.	Settling of mud aggregates.
Fb	Claystone to siltstone bioturbated	Grey to greenish, micaceous, coal clast (mm to <2cm) and locally with bivalves <3cm. Partial to totally bioturbated (BI 2 to 6) by <i>Thalassinoides isp</i> , <i>paradoxicus</i> , <i>saxonicus</i> , tube diameter <1cm, and <i>Rhizocorallium</i> with tube size from 2 to >15cm. Locally <i>Teichichnus</i> , <i>Cylindrichnus</i> , and <i>Macarronichnus</i> . Transitional to abrupt basal contact.	Deposition from suspension. Primary structures obliterated by bioturbation.

Table 1. Siliciclastic depositional facies recognised in Consolação – São Bernardino succession (Magalhães et al., 2023).

Facies Code	Lithology and sedimentary structure	Description	Main process
Fbc	Claystone to siltstone with bioclasts	Grey to greenish, massive, micaceous, with bioclasts of gastropods, bivalves, and oysters. Transitional basal contact.	Deposition from suspension and organisms activity.
Sbc	Sandstone bioclastic	Cream to dark grey, medium- to fine-grained, massive. Bioclastic (fragments of coral, bivalve, oyster, crinoid, and green algae < 5cm), and some agglutinated foraminifera and ostracod. Also oncolite nucleus with echinoid and miliolid foraminifera. Locally coal fragments mm, coarse-grained to granular and bivalve clasts < 2cm. Usually occur as isolated bed or associated with RUD and BND facies. Erosive to abrupt basal contact.	Mixing of clastic grains and bioclastic fragments in shallow marine environment.
WCK/PCK	Wackestone/ Packstone	Cream to light grey, massive to faint laminated. Contains green algae and rare bivalves and ostracods, agglutinated foraminifera, macroforaminifera, miliolids, gastropods. In some samples there are a large number of calcispheres. Locally the amount of bioclasts creates a grain supported framework (Packstone). Scattered fine-grained quartz grains (<10%). In some places with <i>Rhizocorallium commune</i> at the top. Abrupt basal contact.	Suspension process for micrite deposition, low energy shallow water. If calcispheres are present indicate deeper waters.
PCK	Packstone	Cream to light grey, massive, bioclastic, rich in agglutinated macroforaminifera, green and red algae, bivalves, gastropods, ostracods and peloids. Scattered fine-grained quartz grains (<10%). Abrupt basal contact.	Bioclasts deposited with micrite in medium energy shallow water. Coexisting with fine quartz grains.
FLT	Floatstone	Cream to light grey, massive, fragments of oysters, corals, bivalves, and echinoids <5cm. Scattered fine-grained quartz grains (<10%). Coal fragments <2cm, locally bioturbated. Abrupt basal contact.	Mud-supported large bioclasts (>2mm) deposited with micrite in low energy shallow water. Coexisting with fine quartz grains.
RUD	Rudstone	Cream to light grey, massive, fragments of corals, oysters, bivalves, red algae, echinoids, agglutinated foraminifera, peloidal matrix and scattered medium to very-coarse quartz grains (<10%). Also oncolitic with coarse- to very-coarse quartz grains. Oncolite nucleus with green algae, echinoids, bivalves, ostracods, gastropods. Usually overlying Fl or Sm facies. Also occurs associated with Sbc and BND facies. Erosive to abrupt basal contact.	Grain-supported large bioclasts (>2mm) always deposited with micrite in shallow water, medium energy. Coexisting with medium to very-coarse quartz grains.
BND	Boundstone	Cream to light grey, massive, matrix, silt and quartz grains. Composed of corals, oysters, bivalves < 10 cm. Locally with red algae, bivalves, coal fragments < 5cm. Some Boundstone are coral-rich, especially towards the base of the interval. At the medium portions of the interval, Boundstone is oyster-rich with encrusting foraminifera, but with fewer corals and bivalves. Scattered quartz grains (<10%). Usually occurs as isolated bed or associated with RUD and Sbc facies. Abrupt to erosive basal contact.	Patch reefs or isolated bioconstructions, medium- (with matrix) to high-energy (without matrix) shallow water.

Table 2. Mixed and carbonate depositional facies recognised in Consolação – São Bernardino succession (Magalhães et al., 2023).

Facies Association	Facies	Diagnostic sedimentary structures / constituents	Interpretation	
			Ichnofacies	Depositional setting based on Burchette and Wright (1992) and Walker and Plint (1992).
IRC - Inner ramp carbonate	WCK/PCK, FLT, PCK, RUD.	Macro-foraminifera, bivalves, gastropods, echinoids, green algae, peloids, quartz grains.	-	Carbonate deposition in shallow-marine low-energy inner-ramp.
CB - Carbonate build-up	BND, RUD.	Oysters, corals, bivalves.	-	Patch reef on semi-consolidated substrate in shallow-marine low-energy inner-ramp.
SHF - Upper to middle shoreface sandstone	Sh, St, Sr, Sm, Sbc, Gm, Fm, Fl.	Upper part: Sharp-based sandstone bodies, horizontal lamination, trough cross-bedding, usually bioturbated at the top. Lower part: Conformable basal contact, horizontal lamination, trough cross-bedding and ripple cross-lamination. Also massive and locally bioclastic, rich in bivalves, oysters, and corals fragments. Usually bioturbated at the top.	<i>Skolithos</i> BI: 1-5	Combination of high energy of wave and current in subtidal shoreface environment.
LSF - Lower shoreface hummocky cross-stratified sandstone	Shcs, Swr, Sh, St, Fm. Locally He, Sc.	Erosive basal contact, sharp based, concave-down geometry, hummocky cross-stratification, fining-upwards, underlain by erosional surface and gutter casts. Towards the top sandstone is horizontal laminated and bioturbated. Locally convoluted sandstone.	<i>Skolithos</i> BI: 1-2 in Sh facies only	Storm-generated sandstone beds and bioturbated facies deposited in lower shoreface.
OFM - Offshore siltstone	Fm, Fl, Fb. Discrete Fbc, Sm.	Massive and laminated siltstone, bioturbated at the top.	<i>Cruziana</i> , <i>Glossifungites</i> BI: 1-5.	Mud settling and sand deposition in offshore.
ORC - Outer ramp carbonate	WCK/PCK, FLT, PCK, RUD, Sm.	Calcispheres, planctonic foraminifera, red algae, quartz grains, locally massive fine-grained sandstone beds.	-	Carbonate deposition in outer ramp.

Table 3. Facies associations recognised in Consolação – São Bernardino succession (Magalhães et al., 2023).

During field activities, participants will describe and interpret facies associations in specific location along the studied succession. Complementary data such as ichnofacies identification and interpretation and microfossil content are incorporated during these activities aiming to support participant's interpretation (Figs. 4 to 10). The cyclicity and facies associations variability enable participants recognizing stacking patterns and identifying sequence stratigraphic surfaces. Integration of sedimentological logs from the groups triggers discussion on sequence hierarchies and the choice for the best rank that fits reservoir zonation and characterization.

Fig. 4. Sedimentary facies observed in the studied area. (A) Laminated and bioturbated siltstone (*Thalassinoides* close to the pencil, position on the log: 21 m). (B) Massive siltstone (position on the log: 19 m). (C) Hummocky cross-stratified sandstone (position on the log: 98.5 m). (D) Massive sandstone (position on the log: 32 m). (E) Trough cross-stratified sandstone (position on the log: 63

m). (F) Sandstone with ripple cross-lamination (Sr) overlain by sandstone with horizontal lamination (Sh, position on the log: 83.5 m). All photographs are N (right) - S (left) oriented.

Fig. 5 Sedimentary facies observed in the studied area (continuation). (A) Boundstone formed by *Praeexogyra pustulosa* oyster (position on the log: 63.4 m), (B) Boundstone formed by *Calamophylliopsis flabellate* coral (Consolação fort), (C) Rudstone with fine-grained sandstone matrix and oyster fragments (position on the log: 54.8 m). All photographs are N (right) - S (left) oriented.

Fig. 6. Thin sections of carbonate and bioclastic sandstone facies observed in the studied area. (A) Wackestone/Packstone with calcispheres, bivalves and ostracods (polarised light, position on the log: 12 m). (B) Boundstone with oyster fragments (polarised light, position on the log: 63.4 m). (C) Rudstone with oysters, echinoids and fine quartz grains (polarised light, position on the log: 79 m). (D) Packstone with macroforaminifers, gastropods and very-fine quartz grains (polarised light, position on the log: 101 m). (E) Floatstone with fragments of bivalves (polarised light, position on the log: 101.6 m). (F) Bioclastic sandstone with fragments of oyster, algae, crinoid and quartz grains (crossed light, position on the log: 47.5 m).

Fig. 7. Facies associations observed in the studied area. (A) Offshore siltstone (OFM, position on the log: 62 m). (B) Lower shoreface hummocky cross-stratified sandstone (LSF) and heterolithic strata at the top. The erosive base truncates offshore siltstone (OFM, position on the log: 107 m). (C) Upper to middle shoreface sandstone (SHF, position on the log: 90 m). (D) Carbonate build-up (CB) (position on the log: 63 m). (E) Carbonate build-up (CB) forming an oyster reef (*Praeexogyra pustulosa*, 63.4 m). (F) Inner-ramp carbonate (IRC) overlying offshore siltstone (OFM, position on the log: 36 m). Stick is 1.2 m long, and each subdivision equals 20 cm. All photographs are N (right) - S (left) oriented.

A. *Rhizocorallium commune* in epirelief preservation, facies Fb. (37.4 m)

B. Detail of A.

C. Intensely bioturbated facies Fb with *R. commune* in epirelief preservation. (50.2 m)

D. Moderately bioturbated facies Sh, with *Thalassinoides* isp. (50.2 m)

E (left), F (right). Upper bedding plane of Fb facies presenting *Thalassinoides* isp., *R. commune* and *Ophiomorpha nodosa*. (52 m)

G (left), H (right). *Thalassinoides* isp., *Cylindrichnus concentricus*, *Teichichnus* isp. and possible *Macaronichnus segregatis* at contact between a thin sandstone bed and facies Fb. (106.6 – 106.8 m)

A (left), B (right). Large *Thalassinoides* structures (upper bed plane of facies Sb in contact with RUD), characterized by a branched burrow system, unlined, passively filled with coarse sediment different from the host rock, thus characterizing a condensed section that includes a maximum flooding surface. (46.4 m)

C. A network of large *Thalassinoides* in facies Fb/FI, deep penetrating the substrate, with sharp walls, unlined, passively filled with sandstone, and no post-depositional compaction. (46.4 m)

D. Large *Thalassinoides* in facies Fm), unlined, passively filled with sediment different from the host rock and no post-depositional compaction. (62 m)

E. A branched burrow system of large *Thalassinoides* in facies Fb, with sharp walls, unlined, passively filled with sediment derived from above the bed, sharp walls and little or no post-depositional compaction. (98.4 m)

F. Vertical burrows (white arrow) in facies Fb in contact with PCK, apparently a branched burrow system, unlined, passively filled with sediment different from the host rock, characterizing a condensed section that includes a maximum flooding surface. (100.8 m)

G (left), H (right). *Rhizocorallium jenense* in upper bed plane of facies Fb on top of facies PCK shown in F. (101.3 m)

Fig. 8. *Cruziana* Ichnofacies observed in the studied area. The acronyms of depositional facies follow Table 1.

Fig. 9. *Glossifungites* Ichnofacies observed in the studied area. The acronyms of depositional facies follow Table 1.

Fig. 10. *Skolithos* (B-E) and *Scoyenia* (A and F) Ichnofacies observed in the studied area. The acronyms of depositional facies follow Table 1.

6. Stratigraphic analysis based on sequence stratigraphy

Sequence stratigraphy is a stratigraphic analysis method based on recognising stratal stacking patterns using the available data from the study area. Stratal stacking patterns (progradational, aggradational, degradational and retrogradational) are independent of scale and control mechanisms. This approach is based on sedimentary processes and enables the understanding of the distribution pattern of sediments during the evolution of sedimentary basins, as well as the prediction of the occurrence of depositional facies associations beyond the control points. For this reason, sequence stratigraphy is applied to clastic, carbonate and evaporite depositional systems in sedimentary basins formed in the most diverse tectonic settings (Catuneanu, 2006, 2019, 2022; Magalhães et al., 2020, 2021, 2023).

The scale of a stratigraphic analysis may be regional (i.e., low resolution and generally based on seismic data) or local (i.e., high resolution, below seismic resolution and generally based on outcrops, cores or well logs). In high resolution, stacking patterns are recognised through the vertical succession of architectural elements. There are four criteria to identify a high-resolution sequence: i) typical internal transgressive-regressive (T-R) pattern; ii) vertical recurrence of the signature of stacking patterns at each considered hierarchy; iii) trends (non-random distribution) of the vertical arrangement of stacking patterns that determine high-frequency sequences as the basis for defining and building the systems tracts of immediately higher-order sequences; iv) mappability of the stacking patterns and their respective bounding stratigraphic surfaces at each considered hierarchy (Magalhães et al., 2020, 2021; Fragoso et al., 2021).

6.1. Stratigraphic analysis of the Consolação – São Bernardino succession

Since Werner (1986), the Consolação - São Bernardino succession has been interpreted as a regressive siliciclastic interval dominated by clay to silt-rich strata deposited in calm and protected shallow-water environments. On closer examination this succession reveals a more complex stratigraphic record, with high-frequency alternations of sedimentary facies depicting a cyclic stratigraphic pattern. Thus, applying up-to-date sequence stratigraphy concepts allows for a rigorous re-evaluation of previous sedimentary interpretations.

Based on the integration of several methods, such as facies analysis, conventional petrography, macrofossil identification, ichnological and microfossil analysis, Magalhães et al., (2023) subdivided the succession into the upper and lower parts. The lower part, from 0 to 98.5 m, is recognised by the presence of carbonate facies associations. In contrast, the upper part corresponds to the interval from 98.5 to 172 m in which carbonate facies associations are absent. In both portions, the sedimentary record is organised into cycles across multiple scales. Such cycles were considered from the perspective of sequence stratigraphy.

The north-west/south-east orientation of the studied outcrops (Fig. 1) coincides with the depositional dip direction. The lack of outcrops along the depositional strike direction hindered the observation of variations in the depositional systems.

6.1.1. High-frequency cyclicality

Sequences with the highest resolution are characterised as a cycle of changes in facies associations stacking patterns bounded by the recurrence of the same sequence stratigraphic surface in the geological record (Magalhães et al., 2020). In this study, the high-resolution sequences that form the multi-scale stratigraphic

framework were defined based on two assumptions: 1) the cyclic changes in facies associations reflect the shoreline trajectory, and 2) the recurrence of these sequences is organised in an ascending trend that composes the stacking pattern of the immediately higher order sequence, revealing short-term modulation by long-term processes in shoreline shifts.

The lower part of the studied succession exhibits a predominance of offshore siltstone and less frequent carbonate and shoreface sandstone facies associations. This combination agrees with a carbonate-influenced low-energy muddy shelf periodically disturbed by the influx of higher-energy shoreface sand-rich sediments. From bottom to top, the observed vertical stacking consists of high-frequency T-R sequences between 1 to 7 m thick composed of offshore siltstone overlain by shoreface sandstone or inner ramp to carbonate build-up facies. Offshore siltstone represents the high-frequency Transgressive Systems Tract (TST). The frequent occurrence of entirely bioturbated beds on top of this facies association, or the upward increase of bioturbation index, indicates periods of sediment starvation that allowed the development of substrate-controlled *Glossifungites* Ichnofacies, thus supporting the interpretation of a condensed section topped by a maximum flooding surface. The upper contact of high-frequency RST with younger TST is abrupt (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11. The medium-frequency T-R Sequence E. The photograph in perspective shows the southwards progradation of the regressive systems tract. (B and C) Examples of high-frequency T-R sequences from the carbonate-influenced low-energy shelf setting. The transgressive term consists of offshore siltstone (OFM, blue triangle). The regressive tract (red triangle) comprises (B) inner-ramp carbonate (IRC, close view from the interval 35-37 m) or (C) upper to middle shoreface sandstone (SHF, close view

from the interval 88.5-91.5 m). Stick is 1.2 m long, and each subdivision equals 20 cm. All photographs are N (right) - S (left) oriented. Abbreviations: MRS – maximum regressive surface (in blue); MFS – maximum flooding surface; Seq. – Sequence.

The change to high-frequency Regressive Systems Tracts (RST) is marked by the deposition of upper to middle shoreface sandstone or inner-ramp to carbonate build-up facies associations. The increase in terrigenous influx promoted the deposition of laminated and cross-bedded sandstone with *Skolithos* Ichnofacies, characterising the upper to middle shoreface setting (Fig. 12). Carbonate production and deposition probably occurred when terrigenous influx was low, combined with a semi consolidated substrate (*Cruziana* or *Glossifungites* Ichnofacies) and a lag time after transgression (Handford and Loucks, 1993; Jones, 2010). The decrease in sediment supply may have been favoured by autogenic processes that shifted sediment entry points across-strike. In this case, carbonate can thrive when the clastic sediment's entry point is further away. In contrast, when the clastic sediments entry point is close, the succession is dominated by terrigenous siliciclastics (see discussion in Schwartz et al., 2006 and Chanvry et al., 2018).

Fig. 12. Schematic illustrations of the palaeodepositional settings associated with high-frequency sequences in the lower part. (A) Palaeoenvironment at the end of regression, (B) the end of transgression and (C) schematic chronostratigraphic framework in a clastic setting. (D) Palaeoenvironment at the end of regression, (E) end of transgression and (F) chronostratigraphic framework in a carbonate environment. For clarity, carbonate facies associations are only shown in D. Abbreviations: MRS – maximum regressive surface (in blue); CC – correlative conformity (in red); MFS – maximum flooding surface (in green), IRC – inner-ramp carbonate, CB – carbonate build-up, ORC – outer-ramp carbonate.

The upper part of the studied succession consists of offshore siltstone and less frequent lower shoreface hummocky and upper to middle shoreface sandstones. Lower shoreface hummocky cross-stratified sandstone is restricted to the interval between 98.5 to 107 m. The predominance of offshore siltstone reinforces the interpretation of a low-energy setting periodically disturbed by storm events, responsible for the deposition of

lower shoreface hummocky cross-stratified sandstone, or wave action and a high influx of higher-energy upper to middle shoreface sandstone (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13. Orthophotograph showing the general aspect of forced regressive deposits (lower shoreface hummocky cross-stratified sandstone - LSF) scouring transgressive offshore siltstone (OFM) strata from medium-frequency Sequence H. Note the regressive surface of marine erosion (RSME) overlain by lenticular sandstone bodies with hummocky cross-stratification (LSF facies association). No vertical exaggeration. Abbreviations: MRS – maximum regressive surface (in blue); CC – correlative conformity (in red); RSME – regressive surface of marine erosion (in orange); Seq. – Sequence.

From bottom to top, the observed vertical stacking consists of recurrent high-frequency T-R sequences between 3 to 16 m thick composed of transgressive offshore siltstone scoured by forced-regressive lower shoreface hummocky or upper to middle shoreface sandstone (Fig. 13). These shoreface sandstones form sharp-based deposits that exhibit *Skolithos* Ichnofacies and an erosive base. Such features are compatible with storm action or deposition above the fair-weather base level. Moreover, within this interval, the recurrent upward stacking of erosive sandstone overlaying offshore strata suggests such surfaces represent the regressive surface of marine erosion truncating offshore strata (Brunn, 1962; Plint, 1988, 1991; Dominguez

and Wanless, 1991; Myrow, 1992; Plint and Nummedal, 2000). The stacking pattern and trend analyses indicate a regular recurrence of high-frequency TST composed of transgressive low-energy offshore fine-grained background sedimentation scoured by forced-regressive shoreface sandstone deposits.

6.1.2. Medium-frequency and low-frequency sequences

The lower part of the studied succession comprises the medium-frequency T-R sequences A to G (Fig. 14). These sequences compose a distinctive pattern. The TST comprises offshore siltstone. In contrast, the RST consists of amalgamated inner-ramp carbonate, carbonate build-up and upper to middle shoreface sandstone strata that prograde southwards. Sequence G includes strata deposited during forced regression and contains the lowermost high-frequency regression surface of marine erosion at 98.5 m. Besides, it also incorporates the youngest carbonate build-up represented by a *Praeexogyra pustulosa* oyster reef at 101.5 m, overlying an interval of the substrate-controlled *Glossifungites* Ichnofacies. Hence, Sequence G includes the boundary between the lower and upper parts: the regression surface of marine erosion at 98.5 m. This surface truncates a *Cruziana* Ichnofacies interval and marks the upward recurrence of strata deposited during forced regression (i.e., lower shoreface hummocky and upper to middle shoreface sandstone; Fig. 14).

The upper part of the studied succession comprises the medium-frequency sequences H, I, and J. The regressive systems tract of these sequences exhibits strata deposited during high-frequency forced regressions. The sequence I contains the uppermost *Cruziana* Ichnofacies interval at 116 m. Two samples from the offshore siltstone at 161.6 and 164.2 m presented calcareous nannofossils that confirmed its marine palaeodepositional setting. Sequence J is limited at the top by the Lourinhã Formation, the base of which represents the Middle-Upper Jurassic disconformity (Fig. 15; Taylor et al., 2014).

The stacking pattern of medium-frequency T-R sequences A to J forms the low-frequency T-R sequences 1 and 2 (Fig. 14). From bottom to top, the thickening-upward of medium-frequency TSTs from sequences A, B and C comprises the low-frequency TST1 (from 0 to 46.5 m). This trend is concomitant with the upward increase of the Bioturbation Index and the occurrence of *Cruziana* and *Glossifungites* Ichnofacies, thus supporting the definition of the low-frequency maximum flooding surface at 46.5 m (Fig. 14). From this surface upwards, there is a change of stacking pattern. The thickening-upward trend of medium-frequency RSTs and the recurrence of *Skolithos* Ichnofacies from sequences D, E, F, G and H characterise the low-frequency RST1 (from 46.5 to 115.3 m). Therefore, the low-frequency T-R 1 sequence is interpreted from 0 to 115.3 m. From 115.3 m upwards, there is a predominance of medium-frequency TSTs over RSTs from the medium-frequency sequences I and J that forms the low-frequency TST2. The Middle-Upper Jurassic disconformity truncates the top of the low-frequency TST2 at 172 m (Fig. 15).

Fig. 14. Nested sequence architecture of the Consolação - São Bernardino succession. The upward trend of high-frequency (HF) sequences composes medium-frequency (MF) Sequences A to J. This cluster considered the transgressive and regressive trends exhibited by the stacking of facies associations and ichnofacies to define medium-frequency sequence stratigraphic surfaces.

Sequences A to G belong to a carbonate-influenced setting (lower part). In contrast, Sequences H, I and J are part of a storm and wave-influenced environment (upper part). Sequence G includes the boundary between the lower and upper parts: the regression surface of marine erosion at 98.5 m. The studied succession is truncated by the Middle-Upper Jurassic disconformity (red wavy line). Abbreviations: BI - Bioturbation Index; HF - High-frequency sequences; MF - Medium-frequency sequences; Seq. - Medium-frequency sequence code; LF - Low-frequency sequence; ST - Systems Tracts; TST - Transgressive Systems Tract; RST - Regressive Systems Tract; Kim - Kimmeridgian.

Fig. 15. A) The red arrow marks the top of the studied succession (Candeeiros Formation) at the lithological contact with the Lourinhã Formation (based on Taylor et al., 2014). This surface corresponds to the Middle-Upper Jurassic disconformity (position on the log: 172 m). (B) Close-up of the Lourinhã Formation deposits, exhibiting (C) palaeosol levels. Abbreviations: Seq. - Sequence; OFM - offshore siltstone (Candeeiros Formation).

The stacking pattern demonstrated by the vertical recurrence of architectural elements is recognised from the sedimentological logs built by participants, with the support of outcrop's orthophotos. High-frequency sequences are then identified through the internal T-R pattern, its vertical recurrence, the analysis of their trends to identify sequences of immediate superior hierarchy, and the mappability of intervals with the same stacking pattern and bounding surfaces (Magalhães et al., 2020; Fragoso et al., 2021). High-frequency sequences compose medium-frequency systems tracts (Fig. 14). Participants are encouraged to identify medium-frequency candidate sequence stratigraphic surfaces during the presentation of sedimentological logs in front of outcrops and the integration of all sedimentological logs in the hotel. During these debates, participants also discuss the identification of low-frequency sequences.

The stratigraphic refinement achieved through the identification and correlation of high- to low-frequency sequences enables rich discussions regarding reservoir zonation and characterisation. The course's exercises reinforce the high-resolution sequence stratigraphic method and its application in the petroleum industry. At the end of each exercise, a favourable moment is established to discuss strategies focused on selecting the best reservoir to start production in new oil fields and optimising production and increasing of oil recovery factor in mature fields. The exercise on reservoir zonation and identification of an oil zone with original pressure from a mature onshore Brazilian field is worth mentioning. Revising the reservoir zonation and identifying oil zones not yet drained oriented workover operations and in-fill drilling to produce the target oil. These actions triggered an increase in production that rose the oil recovery factor by 5%. Such a real example of field rejuvenation not only proves the advantage of using high-resolution sequence stratigraphy but also motivates participants to apply it in their routines back in office.

7. Final remarks

This is a methodological and practical field course that is founded on the recognition of stacking patterns, identification of sequence stratigraphic surfaces and systems tracts, and the hierarchical ordering of stratigraphic sequences from low-frequency (seismic scale) to high-frequency reservoir zonation and characterisation.

Starting from the "learn by doing" assumption, this course is an opportunity for participants to refine their knowledge and improve their skills in stratigraphic analyses based on up-to-date sequence stratigraphy. Using VOMs to integrate several data with the sedimentological logs enable participants to propose and test interpretations using 3D virtual models, mimicking the current practice in vogue in the industry and academy. High-resolution sequence stratigraphy is the current paradigm of reservoir geology. Experiencing real and concrete situations throughout the course facilitates its comprehension and encourages its application in the participants' work routines. Therefore, the *Field Course Sequence Stratigraphy (Lusitanian Basin) – cyclicity and reservoir zonation in shallow-marine setting* consists of an outstanding training opportunity, experience and learning exchange, perhaps unique in the world.

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